

Development of a National Infrastructure for in-situ wave observations

ARDC AUSTRALIAN DATA PARTNERSHIPS PROGRAM
PROJECT FINAL REPORT

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31/03/2023

CONTENTS

1	PROJECT INFORMATION	2
1.1	Background	2
1.2	Achievement of project aims	3
2	DESCRIPTION OF PROJECT OUTPUTS	4
2.1	Achievements against project work packages:	4
2.2	Project outputs	9
2.3	Outreach and training activities	10
3	SUSTAINABILITY PLAN	11
4	FAIR	12
4.1	Implementation of FAIR Data Guidelines	12
5	PROJECT IMPACT	15
5.1	Communications and Engagement	15
5.2	Research Outcomes Planning	17
6	LESSONS LEARNED	18
6.1	What Went Well?	18
6.2	What Could be Improved?	18

1 PROJECT INFORMATION

INVESTMENT ID	DP748
PROJECT START AND END DATES	January 2021 - April 2023
LEAD ORGANISATION	Australian Ocean Data Network (AODN) - University of Tasmania
PARTNER ORGANISATIONS	NSW Department of Planning, Industry and Environment (NSW-DPE), The University of Western Australia (UWA), RPS MetOcean Pty Ltd, CSIRO (Environment), Bureau of Meteorology (BOM), Deakin University, The University of Melbourne, Pilbara Ports Authority, OMC International, Queensland Department of Environment and Science, Australian Institute of Marine Science (AIMS), Western Australia Department of Transport, Manly Hydraulics Laboratory
PROJECT CONTACT PERSON	Mr Guillaume Galibert

1.1 Background

Wave dynamics are critical to ocean industries, coastal development and leisure activities. Institutions all over Australia collect wave data but only a small subset has previously been available on the Integrated Marine Observing System's (IMOS) Australian Ocean Data Network (AODN) Portal as real-time and delayed mode. In 2018, the marine Research Data Cloud (RDC) project funded by the ARDC enabled the collation, assembly and standardisation of Australia's surface wave buoy collections for near real-time and legacy data from the early 1970s to present. The real-time and delayed mode data available on AODN Portal have been the two collections consistently in the top 15 most downloaded datasets since their release.

Increasing the amount of wave data from a wide range of organisations available via AODN would only be possible with a set of agreed data and metadata standards and a streamlined ingestion and publication process. The proposed data asset in this project aimed to build on the current data collections and enhance their use within and beyond Australia by:

- providing a harmonised, standardised and trustworthy collection of wave measurements collected by a range of platforms to researchers and other stakeholders;
- increasing the amount of wave data openly accessible in adopting the FAIR data principles;

- reviewing, streamlining and documenting the governance arrangements and end-to-end data workflow;
- reviewing current quality control practices and developing best practices for the Australian wave community across the data lifecycle;
- developing metadata and data standards;
- consolidating the delivery of the national collection through the AODN infrastructure and facilitate ingestion and publication by international partners;
- and engaging and contributing to related international initiatives e.g. establishment of a Wave Global Archive under the World Meteorological Organization Expert Team for Coastal and Emergency Response.

The AODN led this Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) project which established a national data asset of Australian in-situ wave observations and improved data delivery to national and international stakeholders. The project partners include research institutions, Government departments and agencies, and private industries.

1.2 Achievement of project aims

The project proposal was to develop a national data asset of Australian in-situ wave observations and facilitate improved data delivery to national and international stakeholders by:

- 1) increasing the amount of publicly available data for real-time and delayed mode data-streams ;

The existing datasets available on the AODN portal [Wave buoys Observations - Australia - near real-time](#) and [Wave buoys Observations - Australia - delayed \(National Wave Archive\)](#) were expanded by adding 4 new data providers organisations. We now have a total of 10 institutions providing data (3 from research institutions/universities, 5 from governmental departments, 2 from industry sector) with a 58% increase of sites for the real-time dataset collection (total number of sites increased from 41 to 65) and a 40% increase of sites for the delayed mode dataset collection (total number of sites increased from 62 to 87).

- 2) reviewing, streamlining and documenting the governance and end-to-end data workflow, allowing submission of data by an expanding range of providers;

Historical workflows with previous partners were reviewed to identify challenges and possible improvements. Based on this review and by considering workflow options for new partners, workflow documents for real-time and delayed mode data across all partners, including the partners' roles and responsibilities, were produced.

A new set of data and metadata standards was developed, for both real-time and delayed mode data, based on a review of existing national and international standards for wave data. These standards allow for scalability in data ingestion and publication at AODN, and simplicity by providing clear guidelines to future partners on how to contribute to the existing dataset collection of integral wave parameters as well as additional dataset collections of wave spectra information and raw displacement of the surface elevation.

3) developing best practices and procedures for quality control (QC), metadata and data formats for legacy and emerging wave measurement systems.

To achieve this, work package 3 leaders first performed a review of published documentation on international quality assurance/quality control (QA/QC) practices and standards before interviewing 6 national organisations that operate wave buoy, spanning government and industry, to understand how wave buoy data is currently being collected and delivered with a particular focus on data formats and QC procedures. The interviews were supported by a previously prepared questionnaire and asked for information on both real-time and delayed mode wave buoy data streams. Their findings were put together in a document which was then discussed in a national workshop with project partners (involving the interviewees as well as other wave data collectors and users). The document summarises the outcomes of the interviews with an aim to understand current procedures as a way to inform the development of a national standard. The final step is to produce a Standard Operational Procedures (SOP) which contains Quality Control routines and information to provide advice on future best practices. This document will be finalised by the project's end date.

2 DESCRIPTION OF PROJECT OUTPUTS

2.1 Achievements against project work packages:

WORK PACKAGE	DETAILS INCLUDING EXPLANATION OF ANY VARIATION	COMPLETION DATE
WP1 – Ingestion and publication of new dataset collections		
Workflow specification (2.1)	AODN and partners have reviewed existing data stream workflows and documented them in the Microsoft Teams project relevant directory , then discussed and agreed on best options for future real time and delayed mode data stream workflows as well as	13/01/2022

WORK PACKAGE	DETAILS INCLUDING EXPLANATION OF ANY VARIATION	COMPLETION DATE
	<p>relevant roles and responsibilities. AODN then formally documented them in the Microsoft Teams project relevant directory.</p>	
Spotter wave buoys (2.2, 2.3, 2.4)	Same as above and specifically for Spotter wave buoys.	13/01/2022
Triaxys wave buoy (2.5, 2.6, 2.7)	Same as above and specifically for Triaxys buoys.	13/01/2022
Dataset collection #1 - NSW Nearshore Wave Buoy Program (2.8, 2.9, 2.10, 2.11, 2.12, 2.13)	<p>The background dataset review has been documented in the Microsoft Teams project relevant spreadsheet. Delayed mode data (integral wave parameters, wave spectra and raw displacement of surface elevation) have been ingested and published on the AODN infrastructure and can be found on AODN THREDDS. Integral wave parameters can be found on the AODN portal in the Wave buoys Observations - Australia - delayed (National Wave Archive) dataset collection.</p> <p>Progress on the ingestion and publication was delayed to include later input from one project partner in order to improve data and metadata standards. No impact on project's overall schedule.</p>	31/10/2022
Dataset collection #2 - Victorian Wave Buoy network (2.14, 2.15, 2.16, 2.17, 2.18, 2.19)	<p>The background dataset review has been documented in the Microsoft Teams project relevant spreadsheet. Delayed mode data (integral wave parameters, wave spectra and raw displacement of surface elevation) have been ingested and published on the AODN infrastructure and can be found on AODN THREDDS for IMOS New Technology Proving Low Cost wave buoys and for the Victorian Wave Buoy network. Integral wave parameters can be found on the AODN portal in the Wave buoys Observations - Australia - delayed (National Wave Archive) dataset collection.</p> <p>Progress on preparing relevant dataset ready for ingestion and publication was delayed due to partner's other competing priorities. No impact on project's overall schedule.</p>	31/03/2023
Dataset collection #3 - UWA wave buoys collection (2.20, 2.21, 2.22, 2.23, 2.24)	<p>The background dataset review has been documented in the Microsoft Teams project relevant spreadsheet. Delayed mode data (integral wave parameters, wave spectra and raw displacement of surface elevation) have been ingested and published on the AODN infrastructure and can be found on AODN THREDDS for IMOS New Technology Proving Low Cost wave buoys and for the UWA wave buoys collection. Integral wave parameters</p>	31/03/2023

WORK PACKAGE	DETAILS INCLUDING EXPLANATION OF ANY VARIATION	COMPLETION DATE
	<p>can be found on the AODN portal in the Wave buoys Observations - Australia - delayed (National Wave Archive) dataset collection.</p> <p>Progress on preparing relevant dataset ready for ingestion and publication was delayed due to partner's other competing priorities. No impact on project's overall schedule.</p>	
Dataset collection #4 - Pilbara Ports Authority (2.25, 2.26, 2.27, 2.28, 2.29)	<p>The background dataset review has been documented in the Microsoft Teams project relevant spreadsheet. Real-time integral wave parameters data is ingested and published on the AODN infrastructure and can be found on AODN THREDDS as well as on the AODN portal in the Wave buoys Observations - Australia - near real-time dataset collection.</p> <p>This task was delayed due to issues with access to the full dataset from the data provider. No impact on project's overall schedule.</p>	07/03/2023
Dataset collection #5 - Subset of private industry data brokered by RPS MetOcean (2.30, 2.31, 2.32, 2.33)	<p>Legal access to a sample dataset from oil and gas industry has not been possible to obtain. Different oil and gas private industries have been considered and contacted with the support of RPS MetOcean and some Steering Committee members, but without success.</p> <p>However, the project successfully demonstrated that access to the Pilbara Ports Authority data (already available via OMC International) using the RPS datafeeds API and certificates is possible.</p>	-
Existing dataset collection on the National Wave Archive (2.34, 2.35, 2.36, 2.37)	<p>Delayed mode integral wave parameters data from historical partners (Queensland Department of Environment and Science, Manly Hydraulics Laboratory, WA Department of Transport and Bureau of Meteorology) have been updated and re-published on the AODN infrastructure. They can be found on the relevant AODN THREDDS directories as well as on the AODN portal in the Wave buoys Observations - Australia - delayed (National Wave Archive) dataset collection.</p>	31/10/2022
WP2 – Development of metadata and data standards		
Background review (3.1)	<p>The review of existing national and international data and metadata standards for real-time and delayed mode wave data is documented in the Microsoft Teams project relevant spreadsheets.</p>	20/08/2021
Dataset collection metadata (3.2)	<p>The metadata records describing Wave buoys Observations - Australia - near real-time and Wave buoys Observations - Australia</p>	02/12/2022

WORK PACKAGE	DETAILS INCLUDING EXPLANATION OF ANY VARIATION	COMPLETION DATE
	<p>- <u>delayed (National Wave Archive)</u> dataset collections of the AODN Portal have been reviewed and updated to reflect the new datasets published in this project.</p> <p>This task was slightly delayed with updates to the metadata records in our production environment waiting for the first additional dataset collections to be published, which had been delayed in the first place. See comments on the following tasks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dataset collection #1 - NSW Nearshore Wave Buoy Program (2.8, 2.9, 2.10, 2.11, 2.12, 2.13), - Data Product #4 - Parameter timeseries (Real-time) (3.12, 3.13, 3.14, 3.15, 3.16, 3.17, 3.18, 3.19) 	
Data Product #1 - Parameter timeseries (Delayed Mode) (3.3, 3.4, 3.5)	A background review of data files used by partners has been documented in the <u>Microsoft Teams project relevant spreadsheet</u> . A metadata and data standard for delayed mode integral wave parameters has been suggested, discussed and agreed with partners through regular 3 weekly catch-up meetings. It has then been formally documented and <u>made publicly available on AODN content storage</u> .	30/11/2021
Data Product #2 - Spectral wave information (Delayed Mode) (3.6, 3.7, 3.8)	A background review of data files used by partners has been documented in the <u>Microsoft Teams project relevant spreadsheet</u> . A metadata and data standard for delayed mode spectral wave information has been suggested, discussed and agreed with partners through regular 3 weekly catch-up meetings. It has then been formally documented and <u>made publicly available on AODN content storage</u> .	14/01/2022
Data Product #3 - Raw displacement of surface elevation (Delayed Mode) (3.9, 3.10, 3.11)	A background review of data files used by partners has been documented in the <u>Microsoft Teams project relevant spreadsheet</u> . A metadata and data standard for delayed mode raw displacement of surface elevation has been suggested, discussed and agreed with partners through regular 3 weekly catch-up meetings. It has then been formally documented and <u>made publicly available on AODN content storage</u> .	14/02/2022
Data Product #4 - Parameter timeseries (Real-time) (3.12, 3.13, 3.14, 3.15, 3.16, 3.17, 3.18, 3.19)	<p>A background review of data files used by partners has been documented in the <u>Microsoft Teams project relevant spreadsheet</u>. A metadata and data standard for real-time integral wave parameters has been suggested, discussed and agreed with partners through regular 3 weekly catch-up meetings. It has then been formally documented and <u>made publicly available on AODN content storage</u>.</p> <p>An open source <u>conversion tool</u> has been developed to ingest real-time data from various relevant Application Programming</p>	02/12/2022

WORK PACKAGE	DETAILS INCLUDING EXPLANATION OF ANY VARIATION	COMPLETION DATE
	<p>Interfaces (APIs) and convert them into the agreed data and metadata standard.</p> <p>Real-time integral wave parameters data have been ingested and published on the AODN infrastructure and can be found on the relevant AODN THREDDS directories as well as on the AODN portal in the Wave buoys Observations - Australia - near real-time dataset collection.</p> <p>Progress on the ingestion and publication was delayed to include later input from one project partner in order to improve data and metadata standards. No impact on project's overall schedule.</p>	
WP3 – Development of Standard Operating Procedures (SOP)		
Background review (4.1)	Published documentation on international QA/QC practices and standards were gathered and reviewed. Then interviews were conducted with wave buoy operators nationally, spanning government and industry, to understand how wave buoy data is currently being collected and delivered with a particular focus on data formats and QA/QC procedures. The interviews were standardised and asked for information on both real-time and delayed mode wave buoy data streams.	30/11/2021
Document QA & QC practices (4.2)	Based on the background review and interviews performed as part of previous task, a summary of existing QA/QC approaches and data formats has been documented in the Microsoft Teams project relevant document.	30/11/2021
Stakeholder engagement (4.3)	<p>A national workshop with project partners took place to involve the interviewees as well as other wave data collectors and users.</p> <p>This workshop was delayed due to participants availability with no impact on project's overall schedule</p>	23/05/2022
SOP (4.4, 4.5)	<p>A Standard Operating Procedure document is currently being finalised. A full draft has been accepted by AODN and is accessible in the Microsoft Teams project relevant document.</p> <p>The production of this document has been delayed due to one work package co-leader moving organisations during the project. The move required additional sub-contracting to be formalised and it impacted the co-leader with additional competing priorities. In addition, on the advice of the project Steering Committee during our last meeting on 24th March, and with agreement from WP3 leaders, the SOP final draft is currently being reviewed by the</p>	31/05/2023

WORK PACKAGE	DETAILS INCLUDING EXPLANATION OF ANY VARIATION	COMPLETION DATE
	<p>Forum for Operational Oceanography (FOO) Surface Wave Working Group (SWWG). Feedback from this national working group will be provided by the 24th of April 2023 so the expected completion date for this task has been extended to the end of May 2023.</p> <p>Note that once the SOP document is finalised, AODN will support WP3 leaders to openly publish it to Ocean Best Practices.</p>	
WP4 – Inventory of wave data collected using Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP) instruments		
Identify data providers (5.1)	<p>A list of 11 known organisations that collect wave data using ADCP instruments was put together by project partners.</p> <p>This task was delayed due to project’s competing priorities with no impact on project overall’s schedule.</p>	28/10/2022
Capture instrument inventory and contributor survey (5.2)	<p>An online survey was put together in collaboration with the project partners to support an ADCP wave data inventory. The survey collected answers from 8 out of 11 contacts.</p> <p>This task was delayed due to project’s competing priorities as well as low responsiveness of survey participants during the summer holiday period. No impact on project’s overall schedule.</p>	17/02/2023
Inventory and recommendations report (5.3)	<p>The results from the ADCP wave data inventory have been documented in the Microsoft Teams project relevant directory.</p> <p>Variation is related to the details described in item 5.2 (row above).</p>	27/02/2023

2.2 Project outputs

- New workflow diagrams and workflow documents with each data provider to record workflow arrangements as well as roles and responsibilities. These are useful for both AODN and the relevant data providers during loss of key staff and onboarding of new staff to these activities so a clear understanding of workflows, roles and responsibilities can be kept and shared.
- Data and metadata standards for the following wave data types have been produced: real-time and delayed mode integral wave parameters, delayed mode wave spectra information, and delayed mode raw displacement of surface elevation. These standards provide guidelines to

current and future data providers on requirements to publish their data openly via AODN. They represent a simplification for both AODN and future data providers to publish wave data openly.

- An open source conversion tool deployed in production at AODN that can ingest and transform real-time data to the agreed data and metadata standards from the following APIs: OMC International, SOFAR and BOM. This tool is critical to scale data ingestion and publication by an increasing number of new organisations willing to share their real-time wave data with AODN.
- Open publication of real-time integral wave parameters from 4 additional organisations. In particular, the data from one new organisation represents a start towards filling a gap of observations in the Australian North West. This data is critical to research in marine science, ocean industries, coastal development and leisure activities.
- Open publication of delayed mode integral wave parameters from 3 additional organisations. Data from 4 historical organisations have been converted to the newly agreed data and metadata standard for consistency in the consolidated dataset collection. This data is of better quality than the real-time equivalent and is critical to research in marine science, ocean industries, and coastal development.
- Open publication of delayed mode wave spectra information as well as raw displacement of surface elevation from 3 organisations. This data allows high level users to perform finer analysis and is critical to research in marine science, ocean industries, and coastal development.
- A Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) which provides recommendations and best practices with regards to QA/QC procedures. This will be useful to build a national community of wave data providers that produces data with consistent QA/QC processes.
- An inventory of wave data providers using ADCP instruments in Australia which includes an audit of their instruments as well as a high level inventory of their data holdings. This will be useful to inform a potential future project that would consist in ingesting and publishing wave data from ADCP instruments.

2.3 Outreach and training activities

ACTIVITY	ACTIVITY DESCRIPTION	NO. OF PARTICIPANTS	DATE OF ACTIVITY
AODN portal workshop at SIMS TAMS course	Workshop targeting the Sydney Institute of Marine Science (SIMS) postgraduate students enrolled in the	60	23/02/2023

	<u>Topics in Australian Marine Science (TAMS) course</u> on how to use the AODN portal to discover, access and download Australian marine datasets.		
AODN portal workshop at IMAS KSA324 course	As above except targeting the Institute of Marine and Antarctic Studies (IMAS) students enrolled in the <u>Oceanographic Methods (KSA324) course</u> .	10	27/02/2023
Display and access to the real-time integral wave data on IMOS OceanCurrent website	Real-time integral wave parameters data is displayed and accessible from <u>the relevant page of IMOS OceanCurrent website</u> .	-	Since April 2022

3 SUSTAINABILITY PLAN

IMOS will continue to play a key role in collecting and publishing wave data in the future:

- IMOS funding from the National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS) has recently been confirmed to cover baseline activities until June 2028. This includes operating 3 existing facilities to collect wave data as well as operating the AODN to ingest, manage and publish wave data.
- In addition, IMOS is currently applying to obtain further fundings from NCRIS with a focus on increasing coastal observations, including wave observations.

Finally, as part of this project and consistently with IMOS practices, workflow documents including information regarding roles and responsibilities of relevant organisations have been produced for each wave data stream. These are key for both AODN and the relevant data providers during loss of key staff and onboarding of new staff to these activities so a clear understanding of workflows, roles and responsibilities can be kept and shared.

4 FAIR

4.1 Implementation of FAIR Data Guidelines

FAIR Data Actions

#	FAIR ACTION	DETAILS OF IMPLEMENTATION
1	All data outputs are assigned appropriate PIDs, preferably a DOI	N/A.
2	All data outputs have metadata to enable discovery	Dataset discovery enabled at the dataset collection level using ISO19115 compliant metadata records published with GeoNetwork.
3	All data outputs have a record in Research Data Australia	All AODN metadata records are automatically harvested by RDA.
4	All data outputs are registered with relevant discipline-specific discovery aggregators (if they exist)	AODN controlled vocabulary published by ARDC is used within ISO19115 compliant metadata records to perform searches on measured parameters, organisations and platforms.
5	The persistent identifier for the data output being described is included in the metadata	N/A.
6	All data outputs are made as openly available as possible; they are only closed where necessary	All data published by the AODN is openly accessible. AODN recommends the use of Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Licence .
7	All data outputs are made available through a repository	All collection datasets described by ISO19115 compliant metadata records (see point 2 above) published with GeoNetwork.
8	All data outputs are available as a download and/or accessible through an open, documented API (where data is not closed)	All data outputs openly available via the AODN portal , but also via the AODN THREDDS catalogue (includes https and opendap services) and OGC compliant web services delivered by the AODN Geoserver . All are well documented open APIs.
9	If the data outputs are not openly available, there is a clear description	N/A.

#	FAIR ACTION	DETAILS OF IMPLEMENTATION
	on the landing page on how to request access to the data outputs and the conditions that need to be met	
10	The persistent identifier for the data output points to a landing page about the data output, even if the data output is not public (open).	N/A.
11	If the data output is not openly available there is an authorisation and authentication procedure to provide access to the data	N/A.
12	The persistent identifier for the data output continues to point to a landing page, even if the data output is no longer available, and there is a policy to maintain these landing pages	N/A.
13	Data outputs use community-agreed standard data formats (where such agreed formats exist)	The project involved an audit of existing wave data formats used nationally and internationally. The best data format used for this project, namely NetCDF, has been discussed and agreed with partners.
14	Metadata for the data output uses community-agreed standards (where such agreed standards exist)	<p>Metadata at the dataset collection level uses ISO-19115, a well known and widely used metadata standard nationally and internationally.</p> <p>Metadata at the dataset level is managed using <u>Climate and Forecast (CF) Convention</u> as well as <u>Attribute Convention for Data Discovery (ACDD)</u>. In addition, specific wave metadata were identified during the audit of metadata standards used for wave data, nationally and internationally. Metadata attributes for wave data were discussed with the partners and agreed to be kept or not, and if kept whether each would be required or only recommended.</p>
15	Data and metadata use community-agreed vocabularies, data models and ontologies (preferably internationally agreed ones where they exist)	Metadata at the dataset collection level uses ISO19115 in combination with AODN controlled vocabularies (which re-use terms from BODC controlled vocabularies when suitable, and submit missing terms for consideration). These are oceanographic community adopted data models and vocabularies considered internationally.

#	FAIR ACTION	DETAILS OF IMPLEMENTATION
		Data and metadata at the dataset level uses CF and ACDD as a widely adopted data model and which include the use of some controlled vocabularies (<u>CF standard names</u> for measured parameters and <u>UDUNITS</u> for units of measured parameters for example). Our suggested data and metadata standard is inspired from the <u>NOAA NCEI NetCDF Templates</u> in that regard.
16	Metadata contains persistent identifiers for research objects and entities (people, organisations) linked to the data outputs (including ORCIDs, grantIDs, RAIDs, DOIs, IGSNs)	We currently don't apply persistent identifiers for research objects, and are yet to implement the inclusion of persistent identifiers for entities in our dataset collection level metadata records.
17	All data outputs are assigned a machine readable licence (preferably CC-BY 4.0)	The licence is detailed at the dataset collection level in an ISO19115 compliant metadata record. The licence is also detailed at the dataset level in the NetCDF file using the relevant ACDD attribute. Both are machine readable.
18	The licence information is available in a machine readable form on the landing page that the persistent identifier (for the data output) refers to	N/A.
19	There is a citation statement for the data output on the landing page that the persistent identifier refers to	N/A. (note - a suggested citation is provided in the dataset collection level metadata record as well as in the dataset level NetCDF file)
20	Provenance information on the data output is attached alongside the data	Metadata at the dataset level (alongside the data) is following CF and ACDD attributes. They cover all required and recommended provenance information agreed with the partners.
21	Relevant discipline-specific metadata to enable reuse is captured and presented alongside the data output following research community best practice	In addition to the above, required and recommended waves data specific attributes, some identified during the wave data format and standard audit, were discussed and agreed with the partners as part of the design of new metadata and data standards for wave data.

5 PROJECT IMPACT

The ARDC and the Government wish to demonstrate the impact on researchers, industry and the general public of the NCRIS investment. Please complete the following sections as relevant to your program.

5.1 Communications and Engagement

ACTIVITY	DETAILS	LINK TO MATERIALS
AODN Technical Advisory Group meeting - 11th May 2021	Overview of the project objectives, highlights of the project plan recently submitted to ARDC.	
Forum for Operational Oceanography - Surface Wave Working Group meeting - 29th July 2021	Overview of the project objectives, update on recent progress and upcoming work.	
AODN report submitted to the National Marine Science Committee - 12th August 2021	Summary of the project objectives and update on progress.	
RPS group news item - 25th October 2021	Communication article "RPS helps to set standards for wave data in new Australian industry-academic collaboration" published on RPS group website	https://www.rpsgroup.com/company/news/rps-helps-to-set-standards-for-wave-data-in-new-australian-industry-academic-collaboration/
Virtual Forum for Operational Oceanography - 22th November and 1st December 2021	Overview of the project objectives, update on recent progress and upcoming work.	
AODN Technical Advisory Group meeting - 30th November 2021	Summary of the project objectives, update on recent progress and upcoming work.	
Scientific publication - expected publication date in March 2022	The present text in the 'Data Records' section of the manuscript referring to the ARDC project is as below, with the intention to inform readers of the national project and that NSW-DPIE wave data will also	Kinsela, M.A. <i>et al.</i> Nearshore wave buoy data for coastal research and management in southeast Australia. <i>Scientific Data</i> . In Revision.

	<p>be available on AODN at the conclusion of the project: “The in-progress Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) project – <i>Development of a national infrastructure for in-situ wave observations</i> – will deliver nationally consistent wave buoy data through the Australian Ocean Data Network (AODN)⁴⁵. All nearshore wave buoy data will also be made available within the national wave dataset upon project completion.”</p>	
IMOS Annual Planning Meeting - 4th March 2022	Overview of the project objectives, existing partners, expected outcomes.	
AODN Technical Advisory Group meeting - 17th May 2022	Summary of the project objectives, update on recent progress and upcoming work.	
AODN report submitted to the National Marine Science Committee - 27th July 2022	Summary of the project objectives and update on progress.	
IMOS Annual Planning Meeting - September 2022	Summary of the project objectives and update on progress.	
AODN report submitted to the National Marine Science Committee - 19th October 2022	Summary of the project objectives and update on progress.	
AODN Technical Advisory Group meeting - 14th November 2022	Summary of the project objectives, update on recent progress and upcoming work.	
Forum for Operational Oceanography / Australian Coastal and Oceans Modelling and Observations Combined Workshop - 21-23th November 2022	Abstract submitted and oral presentation. Overview of the project objectives, update on progress and outputs.	https://conferences.com.au/catching-waves-development-of-a-national-infrastructure-for-in-situ-wave-observations/
AODN report submitted to the National Marine Science Committee - 10th February 2023	Summary of the project objectives and update on progress.	

Forum for Operational Oceanography - Surface Wave Working Group meeting - February 2023	Summary of the project objectives, update on progress and outputs.	
IMOS Annual Planning Meeting - March 2023	Summary of the project objectives and update on progress.	

5.2 Research Outcomes Planning

ACTIVITY	DETAILS
Establishment of a monitoring framework (for project outcomes and impacts)	<p>The already-established IMOS Impact Database has been altered to accommodate this project. Any outcome or use that is reported against this project (via the reporting form or other mechanism) will be entered into the system and will form part of the impact reporting processes regularly undertaken by the IMOS Office.</p> <p>The metrics from these processes will be made available to ARDC.</p>
Inputs from research users in design of the infrastructure	Options for design of the infrastructure and workflows were discussed with partners.
Partnerships with research translation specialists	The OceanCurrent sub-facility of IMOS is led by CSIRO and aims at providing up to date ocean information around Australia, having direct societal impacts on fishing and marine recreational activities for example. Wave data currently available at AODN will be added to their scope in April 2022. When ready, AODN will work with them so they can include the new wave datasets made available during this project.
Establishment of policies, systems and workflows to track uptake (of project outcomes)	<p>IMOS defines a 'use' of data as a tangible outcome, such as a publication, model, postgraduate project, or reported applied use by a member of the public. Once reported to the IMOS Office (see 'Establishment of a monitoring framework' above), the IMOS Impact Analysis then tracks and analyses uptake and impact.</p> <p>Where uses are not reported, the IMOS Office uses trawling software to search for key terms related to the product (e.g. "Waves AND IMOS") and processes any outputs that are discovered.</p>
Participation in the ARDC Impact Reporting Working Group (if applicable)	Former IMOS Deputy Director Indi Hodgson-Johnston attended the ARDC Impact Reporting Working Group meetings and has also presented on the impact tracking work at the NESSF Information Standards Advisory Panel.

6 LESSONS LEARNED

6.1 What Went Well?

- Implementation of monitoring and control tools (regular progress reports and Gantt chart) really helped in project management activities to follow up on tasks from a great number of partners and to remind them on a regular basis about their upcoming tasks and priorities.
- Keeping regular (3 weekly) catch-up meetings with the partners enabled to continuously inform them with the project progress and to engage with them on the current tasks and help with removing blockers when relevant.
- The project Steering Committee understood the challenges faced during the project and were able to assist project management by either providing advice or taking action to help removing blockers.

6.2 What Could be Improved?

- An important change to the project as originally planned was that one key partner could not eventually commit technical resources to support ingestion and publication of real-time data. This was identified as a dependency in the project plan but not quite as a risk with mitigation strategy. Yet, a project variation was possible and accepted, and the main project outcomes for real-time data ingestion and delivery were still successfully delivered. It is a reminder that starting a project without all Collaboration Agreements with key project partners finalised (especially when the partner's organisation requires a formal one) represents a significant risk to the scope and schedule of the project. In addition, it is critical to get confirmation from partners' technical teams that they will be available to participate in the project during the project time period.
- Seeking a legal data sharing agreement with the oil and gas industry has proven to be difficult and remains a challenge for the future. Two oil and gas industries were considered from the partners' networks, unfortunately for both of them their legal department (and project partners) refused to sign a data sharing agreement. This was identified as a risk in the project plan and after reflection should have been assessed with a High likelihood rather than Medium. All mitigation actions identified at the time were taken. Similarly to the lesson learnt above, starting a project without all Data Sharing Agreements with key project partners finalised (especially when the organisation requires a legal one) represents a significant risk to the scope and schedule of the project.